

#3

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

PERSONAS: UNDERSTANDING OUR STAKEHOLDERS

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Crucial at project development stage and used iteratively throughout the interactive innovation process.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small groups or large consortia.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Non-expert users, no technical knowledge required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>30 mins-2 hrs mins (depending on group size & extent of discussion). At least one facilitator is required.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials, although professional graphic design of personas is optional. Can be conducted physically with participants in a room or on an online platform such as Klaxoon, Pinup, or Mural.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools #1, 5, 19, 20, 26, 27, 28.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Photo by Judith Prins on Unsplash

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Sensitise actors involved in interactive innovation projects to the circumstances, challenges, innovation needs etc. of their stakeholders.
- To profile the whole range of stakeholders, and to understand their different circumstances/needs etc.
- To provide a tool to continuously revisit (throughout the interactive innovation process how well the project is responding to the realities, circumstances, needs etc. of stakeholders

Background and Logic

Multi-actor projects involve diverse actors who are directly involved in interactive innovation (and can represent different actor types in the process). However, not everyone can be directly involved in multi-actor projects, and projects (particularly publicly funded projects) need to be constantly mindful of their stakeholders. What is the full range of stakeholders? What are their circumstances, innovation challenges & needs? Profiling the range of stakeholders, using a persona template to bring them 'to life' sensitises actors involved in projects to stakeholder cohorts they are innovating for. As actors gain more insights to stakeholder circumstances, needs etc., over the lifetime of a project, personas can be modified and their range diversified. Personas can be revisited in interactive innovation processes, to support actors' attentiveness to their circumstances and needs etc. It is important that stakeholder profiling exercises take into account gender and diversity issues in how stakeholders are identified and profiled.

This tool can be used in conjunction with Tool #5 (needs register) and other tools that map stakeholders, e.g. Tools # 1, 26, 27, 28. The Tool to appraise gender and diversity (Tool #20) is important to ensure balance in how personas are selected and developed.

Materials

- Flip chart paper
- Thick dark markers
- Online persona generator (e.g. Mural) - optional.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Brainstorming Stakeholders

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the exercise.
- Ask participants to brainstorm the stakeholders/end-users who will use innovations/knowledge generated by the project.
- 'Who will use our new innovations & knowledge in wider society?'

Step 2: Develop Personas

- For each of the stakeholder types identified, develop a persona or two or more personas (taking into account sub-types of stakeholders and gender, it may be appropriate to develop more than one persona per stakeholder category).
- If there are many stakeholder types identified, ask participants to work in pairs/small groups to develop the personas.
- It may be appropriate to ask participants who are particularly familiar with particular stakeholder types to develop personas for those types.
- The initial questions to lead participants to create a persona should focus directly on bringing the persona 'to life'. These are questions such as:
 - » What is his/her name?
 - » Age?
 - » Location/address
 - » What kind of house do they live in?
 - » Family members?

Step 2: Persona Template

- Participants can use flip chart paper to create the personas, using pre-defined headings/questions as well as any other headings/questions participants wish to add.
- It should take no longer than 20 mins to develop a single persona. Participants should be encouraged to work quickly, providing 'gut instinct' insights. Several personas may be developed per stakeholder type, to reflect diversity within types.
- An example of possible headings/questions, which can be customized to the project/stakeholder type, is as follows:

